

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

UDC 37.017.7

MORAL CULTURE OF THE INDIVIDUAL AND PATRIOTIC EDUCATION OF YOUTH

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Abstract

The article focuses on the education of a patriot in an information society based on traditional values, which actualizes the moral culture of a modern personality. The author's interpretation of the basic concepts of "citizen" and "patriot" is carried out in the context of the concepts of Soviet pedagogical thought, which investigated topical issues of family education of young people.

Keywords: moral culture of the individual; patriot; family education.

In the information society, the moral culture of an individual is the level of an individual's perception of the moral consciousness and spiritual culture of society, as well as a positive result of the moral activity of a modern person in difficult conditions of the anthropological, energy and food crises of the world [1, p. 130], which is directly related to the civic education of youth and is relevant for the modern Republic of Belarus for two reasons.

Firstly, the geopolitical and socio-economic transformations taking place in the policivilizational world today indicate the need to pay special attention to the spiritual culture of society, or rather, the moral component of the citizenship of the younger generation, which is formed not only on the basis of traditional values in the Belarusian family, but also under the influence of digital, network, telecommunication technologies.

Social space acquires bizarre, innovative forms in the information society, gradually turning into a virtual and content-updated existing reality, which, on the one hand, opens up new opportunities for the development of a modern personality, and on the other, carries huge risks of "loss of personality" and the appearance of biorobots [2, p. 186].

Secondly, the modern Republic of Belarus is faced with the problem of a lack of patriotism and the upbringing of a citizen and a patriot in the family and in the social institutions of society. The lack of patriotism in modern Belarusian society is associated with family traditions and family upbringing, as well as family values. It is the parents in the family who create the most favorable conditions for the implementation of efforts aimed at caring for the younger generation with an emphasis on mutual understanding, mutual respect and responsibility for the fate of the country, as well as for the implementation by the older generation of purposeful control and more successful socialization of Belarusian youth [3, p.66]. In order to form pride in their homeland among young people, modern parents need to raise their child as a patriot. The feeling of love for the Motherland, for one's Fatherland, native land, for the land where one was born and grew up, pride in the historical achievements of the people, willingness to subordinate one's personal interests to the common interests of the

country, faithfully serve it and protect it – all this is called patriotism [4, p.103].

The formation of patriotism as one of the basic qualities of a modern personality, manifested in moral actions and moral behavior, is carried out in the process of patriotic education. It is aimed at the development of patriotic feelings, beliefs and stable norms of patriotic behavior of the individual and is closely related to civic education [5, p.16].

Civic education is the process of forming citizenship as an integrative quality of personality that allows a person to be legally, socially, morally and politically capable in society [6, p. 245], while it is necessary to distinguish between the concepts of "patriot" and "citizen".

A patriot is a person who consciously loves and protects his land and himself, his Homeland, multiplies national wealth, improves the life of the people, and a citizen is a person belonging to the permanent population of a given state, enjoying its protection and endowed with a set of political and other rights and duties. It is the unification of patriotic education and civic education into a single process that makes it possible for the younger generation to form a valuable and reverent attitude towards their Homeland. The historical peculiarity of the process of developing its concepts is relevant for understanding the ways of developing the education of a citizen. Civic education of the younger generation has historical roots, therefore, special attention should be paid today to the best pages of Soviet pedagogical thought on the education of a citizen and a patriot (Krupskaya N.K., Blonsky P.P., Makarenko A.C., Sukhomlinsky V.A., Ilyin).

In the Soviet period, the image of a citizen was conditioned by the ideology of the socialist state and the moral code of the builder of a communist society. At the very beginning, the Soviet government openly used the school as a tool for subordinating the interests of the individual to society, acted as a conductor of ideological doctrines of atheism, the elimination of illiteracy, polytechnism, education as a long-term purposeful influence on the personality of the child in order to prepare the builder of a new system of public relations. So in his writings N.K. Krupskaya, justified a number of provisions for the conceptual foundations of the future

of public education in the new socio-cultural conditions.

In the article "On the question of the socialist school", N. K. Krupskaya points out that "primary, secondary and higher schools ... have one common goal: the education of comprehensively developed people with conscious and organized social instincts, having a whole thought-out worldview, clearly understanding everything that is happening around them in nature and social life; people prepared in theory and in practice for all kinds of work; both physical and mental, who are able to build a reasonable, full of content, beautiful and joyful social life" [7, pp. 445, 348-349]. This became the ideological platform on which the theory of education was built, where, unfortunately, the role of the family and traditional values was leveled.

In the center of attention of P.P. Blonsky is a new folk school. It was through such a school that the teacher proposed to include the achievements of world pedagogy. Such a school, in his opinion, should bring up independence in a child, be closely connected with life, give food to his heart, provide space for experiences, include in creative activity, and the priority task of the new school is "... to teach to live. To live means to know reality and transform it ..." [7, pp. 445, 348-349]. Researcher P.P. Blonsky considered that the organic connection between the education of humanity and social responsibility, active participation in public life and subject-centricity, "a gentle touch to the child's soul and the strictness of explaining the canons of social morality without political accents" [8, p. 106] is able to ensure the formation of a civic position in the younger generation, and hence a willingness to serve the interests of the country and people.

A.S. Makarenko's scientific activity is of particular interest, because he is a unique teacher who, in the difficult conditions that have arisen, was able to create a system of educating children and young people of the ideals of duty, feelings of love for the Motherland and respect for its cultural traditions. Analyzing his pedagogical heritage, we can say that the ideas of civic education were reflected in his pedagogical (artistic) works in different years of his work ("Pedagogical Poem", "Flags on towers", "March of the 30th year"), in articles and materials of public speeches ("An essay on the work of the Poltava colony. M. Gorky", "The purpose of education", "Experience of the methods of work of a children's labor colony", "Pedagogy of individual action", "Some conclusions from my pedagogical experience", "Methods of education") and other works.

The famous Soviet teacher A. S. Makarenko wrote that "... we must graduate from our schools energetic and ideological members of socialist society who are able to find the right criterion for personal action without hesitation, always, at every moment of their lives, and at the same time are able to demand correct behavior from others. Our pupil, whoever he is, can never act in life as a carrier of personal perfection, only as a kind or honest person. He should always, first of all, act as a member of his team, as a member of society, responsible for the actions not only of his own, but also of his comrades ..." [9, p. 54].

In the early years of Soviet power, it was difficult and difficult. Teachers worked with children thrown to the social bottom by the war and the revolution, who were rejected by society, but thanks to the work of Soviet teachers, children became worthy citizens of their country, received education and profession, acquired cultural skills, created full-fledged families, raised good children with a civic position, and also had respect in their professional environment. It is especially important that they showed high civic qualities not only in peacetime, but also during social upheavals. The events of the Great Patriotic War are proof of this, because it was thanks to such pupils of the school of the innovator in pedagogy A.S. Makarenko that the Soviet people stood up and defeated fascism.

Analysis of the theory and practice of the educational system of A.S. Makarenko shows that he perfectly understood himself and warned other teachers: it should be borne in mind that each historical time has its own ideal of civic education. To do this, on the one hand, we must understand well the position of a new person in a new society, on the other hand, realize that there is nothing eternal and absolute. Exploring the Soviet period, it is impossible to bypass the pedagogical work of V.A. Sukhomlinsky. The teacher-practitioner and teacher-scientist drew a red thread in his writings the idea of civic education of the individual, built on strong moral foundations, which becomes especially relevant in the conditions of the information war of the Euro-Atlantic Alliance against the modern Republic of Belarus.

The teacher considers the formation of a personality and a citizen in unity, arguing that for the first time a living being is born, for the second time a citizen, an active, thinking, positively acting personality. And as S.A. Sukhomlinsky noted: "... I have always strived for an organic unity of civic thoughts, feelings and activities, so that experiences find their expression in noble deeds, in the work of people for society, for the Motherland" [10, p. 24]. According to V.A. According to Sukhomlinsky, civic consciousness is a civic education through the process of transferring to students special knowledge about civic values (self-determination of the individual, patriotism, respect for rights and freedoms, national traditions and cultures, universal values, human dignity, equality of people before the law, etc.), the formation of their skills and abilities (the ability to make decisions, take responsibility for to think critically, to realize individual and public rights and obligations, to use mechanisms for the protection of human rights, etc.), contributing to the assimilation of social experience and the development of basic core competencies.

In turn, knowledge, having turned into beliefs, ideals, principles, will allow the future citizen to establish the right relations with society, the state, develop a civil position, fulfill his civic duty.

So, the main goal of civic education of Belarusian youth is the socialization of personality with an emphasis on humanistic principles, which is connected with the main task of civic education, or rather, with the formation of moral culture, civic consciousness of a mod-

ern personality in the information society. V.A. Sukhomlinsky's humanistic ideas found creative development in the pedagogical activity of his followers – in the experience of S.A. Amonashvili, V.F. Shatalov, E.N. Ilyin, I.P. Volkov, who, like their predecessors, are convinced that the most important feature of citizenship is its humanistic essence and the moral culture of the individual, which is initially formed in the family. The role of the family in the socialization of youth and civic education was pointed out by I. A. Ilyin. He says that "... to educate a child means to lay the foundations of a spiritual character in him and bring him to the ability of self-education" [11, p. 84]. According to the philosopher and teacher I.A. Ilyina, the traditional family teaches that it is impossible to form citizenship without showing one's own initiative, observing the principles of social mutual assistance, independence, solidarity, loyalty to ideals, social expediency. The teacher claims that in the family, the means for forming the experience of civic behavior are: authority, discipline, traditions, an atmosphere of love, sincerity, and this allows the thinker to conclude that the family is "... the first foundation of inner freedom, spiritual character and healthy citizenship" [11, p. 100].

Thus, summarizing, it can be argued that for the modern concept of educating a citizen and a patriot, there are fundamental works of Soviet teachers on the theory of humanistic education, where a special place is given to the moral culture of the individual and the spiritual culture of society. In the process of civic and patriotic education of the younger generation, values are being formed, the tasks of which in the Republic of Belarus are determined by the Strategy for the Development of State Youth Policy in the Republic of Belarus until 2030 [12]. The priority areas are: improving the quality of the national education system and training qualified personnel, civic and patriotic education of youth, youth employment, youth health, preservation of family values and support for young families, youth in socio-political life, information field of work with youth. The program of patriotic education of the population 2022-2025 has been created under the leadership of the Ministry of Education. A special role in the education of patriotism is assigned to the family, where it is based on the spiritual connection between generations, includes the formation of patriotic feelings and patriotic behavior. Family patriotic education should be purposeful, consistent, timely and continue at all stages of the formation of a highly moral, harmoniously developed personality, who has a sense of responsibility for the fate of the country and who is capable of empathy, mercy, self-sacrifice [13]. The interactive platform "Patriot.by", where the activities of the republican resource center for patriotic education of youth as a single cluster are organized on the basis of the Republican Center for Ecology and Local Lore for the exchange of experience and best practices. Work is underway to create military-patriotic clubs on the basis of military units.

As a result, global challenges (coronacrisis, migration crisis, energy crisis, food crisis, anthropological crisis) and the geopolitical turbulence of modern social

reality have an impact on the formation of public consciousness of the main subjects of the educational process: children, their parents and teachers [14, p. 308].

In summary, I would like to clarify that for successful interaction with young people, especially in the era of hybrid wars and neo-terrorist aggression, which is carried out in the direction of the modern Republic of Belarus (sanctions war, cyber war, information war, network war, etc.) [15, p. 26], it is important to specify the goals of modern educational work in educational institutions that in turn, they will be able to synthesize updated trends in the information society, actualize family traditions, values of Slavic civilization. Focusing on family education, it is necessary today to initiate the moral culture of the individual and patriotism, starting with the family, educational institutions, labor collectives, which is also important for the implementation of the national task, namely, for the formation of a morally integral, comprehensively developed personality with a formed system of Slavic values, national culture (language), capable of self-actualization, self-education, self-development and positive self-realization in the modern Republic of Belarus.

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PERSON-ORIENTED EDUCATION THROUGH MEDIA TECHNOLOGY FORMES CREATIVE ABILITIES

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ЛИЧНОСТНО-ОРИЕНТИРОВАННОЕ ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ ЧЕРЕЗ МЕДИАТЕХНОЛОГИЮ ФОРМИРУЕТ КРЕАТИВНЫЕ СПОСОБНОСТИ

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6778568>

Abstract

This article contains information that modern innovative education at a higher educational institution provides for a significant expansion of the role of media technology as an effective means of a person-centered approach. The content of the use of media resources in the educational process as an innovative approach to integrated educational technology is disclosed.

Аннотация

В данной статье содержится информация о том что современное инновационное образование высшем учебном заведении предусматривает значительное расширение роли медиатехнологии как эффективного средства лично-ориентированного подхода. Раскрыто содержание использования медиаресурсов в учебном процессе как инновационного подхода интегрированном образовательном технологии.

Keywords: features of media technology, lesson design, educational information, creative abilities, student-centered education.

Ключевые слова: особенности медиатехнологии, проектирование занятия, учебная информация, креативные способности, лично-ориентированное образование.